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A STUDY ON INVESTMENT BEHAVIOUR OF WOMEN EMPLOYEES WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO KOZHIKODE DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

Investment is a sacrifice of current money or other resources for future benefits. Numerous avenues of investment are available today. Two key aspects of any investment are time and risk. The object of the investor is to minimize the risk involved in investment and maximize the return. Wealth creation and accumulation of wealth are the objectives of investment. Kerala is a state where proportion of men and women are almost equal. And the numbers of working women are increasing in our state. Kozhikode is one among the district of Kerala where there are large number of women employees working in different fields such as banks, colleges, schools, government department and other private institutions. This study is conducted to identify the investment behaviour of women employees and their risk taking capacity.

Key words: Investment alternatives, occupation, risk, return

INTRODUCTION

Investment means purchase of some financial assets that yield a return, which is proportionate to risk assumed over some future period of time. It is an economic activity fascinates people from all walks of life regardless of their education, status, occupation, family background etc. However, all the people who make investment do not benefit from it. Majority of the investors may incur losses. Those who incur losses do not manage their investment scientifically, instead they follow others blindly. They probably are unaware of the fact that

investing is a science as well as an art. In order to benefit from investment one must acquire the requisite skills and their application.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

People make investment for a variety of purposes. The objective of investment should be clearly understood before initiating the process of investment. The objective of investment may be income, capital appreciation or a future provision for contingencies etc. Based on the objectives investment avenues will be chosen. Now a day the proportion of investment made by the women employees in Kerala is increasing. Among various districts of Kerala, Kozhikode is also one among the district where there lot of women employees and investment done by women employees are also increasing. In this situation there is a need to know about the investment behaviour of women employees and factors considered by them while choosing the investment avenues. And also to know whether occupation and age of women employees makes any change in their investment behaviour and to identify the risk taking capacity of women employees.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study the investment behavior of women employees belonging to different occupation.
- To identify the factors that influence women investor to choose different investment avenues.
- To know whether women employees are aware about the market conditions.
- To determine risk taking ability of women investors.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

- There is no significant difference in the investment behavior of women employees with regard to their occupation.
- Age group of women investors does not influence their risk taking power.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND DATA BASE

The study is designed as descriptive one based on both primary and secondary data. Primary data required for the study are collected using questionnaire and secondary data required for the study are collected from books, internet etc.

Sample Design

A sample of 80 is selected from among the women employees of Kozhikode District using convenient sampling method.

Tools used for Data Collection

A well structured questionnaire was designed to collect data from women investors

Tools for Data Analysis

For the purpose of data analysis the following statistical and mathematical techniques were used:

- Percentage Analysis
- Chi square test
- Weighted average method

List of variables undertaken for the study

- Age group
- Occupation
- Risk
- Return
- Market awareness

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

As in the case of almost all social science research, this study is also not free from certain inherent limitations as to:

1. Study is originally based on the data supplied by the women investors; its reliability influences the findings of the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The primary data collected were edited, tabulated and analysed and the results obtained are presented below.

Age group

In order to identify whether age group influence women investors in any manner while taking a decision about investment, sufficient information are collected and is shown in the table below:

Table No. 1: showing the age wise classification of women investors

Age	No.	Per cent
Below 25	13	16
25-35	20	25
35-45	24	30
45-55	12	15
55 and above	11	14
TOTAL	80	100

Majority of the women investors (30%) belongs to the age group of 35-45. 25% of belongs to the age group of 25-35, 16% belongs to age group below 25, 15% belongs to the age group 45-55 and 14 % belongs to the age group of 55& above.

Occupation

The following table shows the occupation of women investors

Table No. 2 Distribution showing the occupation of women investors.

Occupation	No.	Per cent
Government employee	18	22
Business	7	9
Private jobs	14	18
Teacher	25	31
Bank employee	16	20
TOTAL	80	100

Among the total women investors selected 22% are government employees, 9% are business women, 18% are private employees, 31% are teachers and 20% are bank employees.

Investment alternatives

Lot of investment alternatives are available in our economy. In order to identify which are the most preferred investment alternatives by women investors, following information are collected

Table No.3 Distribution showing various investment alternatives chosen by women employees.

Investment alternatives	No.	Per cent
Bank deposit	35	44
Shares	7	9
Gold	15	19
Real estate	1	1
Mutual fund	8	10
Insurance policies	14	17
TOTAL	80	100

Most preferred investment alternative of women employees (44%) are bank deposits. Second preferred is gold (19%). It is interesting to note that only 1% of the women investors choose real estate as an investment alternative.

Occupation influence Investment Decision

To identify the occupation influence the investment decision of women employees, some data are collected and are tabulated in such a manner to analyse them using Chi-square test

Table no. 4 Distribution showing occupation influence investment decision

	Govt. employee	Business	Private jobs	Teacher	Bank employee	Total
Bank deposit	8	0	7	14	6	35
Shares	0	3	2	2	0	7
Gold	7	2	0	5	1	15
Real estate	0	0	0	1	0	1
Mutual fund	0	2	2	0	4	8
Insurance policies	3	0	3	3	5	14
Total	18	7	14	25	16	80

Chi square value: 41.50, df:20, P-value: 0.0032

In order to know whether there is any difference in the investment decision taken by the women investors belonging to different occupation, following hypothesis was formulated and is tested using chi-square test.

H₀: There is no significant difference in the investment behavior of women employees with regard to their occupation.

As the p-value obtained at degrees of freedom 20 is 0.0032, which is less than 0.05 null hypothesis formulated will be rejected. So it can be concluded that occupation of women investors influence the investment decision taken by them.

Factors considered while choosing investment alternative

To determine the factors considered by women employees while choosing investment alternatives, certain factors were identified and they were asked to rank them according to their consideration.

Table No.5 Distribution of weighted average of factors considered by women investors

Factors	Total weight	Weighted average	Rank
Low risk	328	21.87	1
Liquidity	176	11.73	5
Tax evasion	208	13.87	3
High returns	300	20	2
Safety	188	12.5	4

In order to identify the factors considered by women investors while selecting the investment alternatives, they were asked to rank the factors in the manner they consider. Weights are assigned to each factor on the basis of the ranks given. Highest rank is given the weight five, then four given to next highest rank and so on. In this manner weights are assigned to each factor. Sum total of the weight of each factors are shown in the column, total weight. Weighted average is obtained by dividing total weight by 15 (5+4+3+2+1). The ranks are given on the basis of weighted average; the factor having highest weighted average is given the first rank and so on.

As per the table highest rank is for the factor low risk, then high return, tax evasion, safety and liquidity.

Market Awareness

There is a need to know the level of awareness of women investors about the existing market conditions.

Table No.6 showing awareness of women investors about existing market conditions.

Aware	No.	Per cent
Fully aware	25	31
Not so aware	45	56
Not at all aware	10	13
Total	80	100

Majority of the women investors (56%) are not so aware about the existing market conditions. Only 31% of the women investors are fully aware about the market.

Risk Taking

The following table shows the opinion of women investors about their risk taking power.

Table no.6 Distribution showing risk taking ability of women investors

Risk	No.	Per cent
High	20	25
Average	11	14
Low	49	61
Total	80	100

As per the above table it is clear that majority of the women investors (61%) are not ready to undertake risk. Their risk taking power is low. Only one fourth of the women investors are ready to undertake high risk.

Risk taking power and age group

In order to determine whether age group of women investors influence their risk taking power, certain information are collected and is tabulated in such a manner to analyse them using chi-square test.

Table no.7 Distribution showing age group influence the risk taking power of women investors

	Below 25	25-35	35-45	45-55	55& above	Total
High	0	14	3	3	0	20
Average	5	2	1	2	1	11
Low	8	4	20	7	10	49
Total	13	20	24	12	11	80

Chi square value: 40.59, df:8, P-value: 0.00000248

In order to test whether the age group of women investors influence their risk power, following hypothesis was formulated:

H₀: Age group of women investors does not influence their risk taking power.

As p-value obtained at degrees of freedom 8 is 0.00000248 is less than 0.05, null hypothesis formulated is rejected. So it can be concluded that risk taking power of women investors are influenced by their age group.

FINDINGS

On the basis of results obtained from the analysis, the major findings are as follows.

- Most of the women investor belongs to the age group of 35-45.
- Occupation of majority of women investors are teaching, Government employee and bank employee.

- Most preferred investment alternatives of women employees are bank deposits, gold and insurance policies.
- Occupation of women investors influences their investment decision. That means according to the changes in the occupation of women investors, there is corresponding changes in their selection of investment alternatives.
- Main factors considered by women investors at the time of choosing investment alternatives are low risk, high return and tax evasion.
- Most of the women investors are not so aware about the existing market conditions.
- Risk taking powers of women investors are low.
- The age groups of women investors influence their risk taking power.

CONCLUSION

Kerala is a state where there are an equal proportion of men and women. And number of women employees increased in the entire sector. And due to this reason the number of women investors had also increased. But there is no change in the attitude of women investors. They are still sticking on safer investment avenues such bank deposits and gold. Majority of the women investors are not ready to undertake risky investment avenues such as share, real estate etc.

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